

Essential and desired metadata for OA books and chapters			
Field name	Field desc	Field type	Status
Essential			
work type	Work Type (e.g. Edited Collection, Monograph)	Controlled Vocabulary, with the option to add free text	Required
work status	Work Status (e.g. published, forthcoming)	Controlled Vocabulary	Required
title	Title	Free text - separate fields for title and subtitle	Required
subtitle	Subtitle	Free text - separate fields for title and subtitle	Required
contributor names	Author/Editor/other contributor name(s) & ORCIDs (where available)	Free text, divided into Given Name(s) and Family Name(s)	Required
contribution type	role description	Controlled Vocabulary, implementing CReDIT, with the option to include additional roles not covered by the CReDIT taxonomy to accommodate needs from the Social Sciences and Humanities	Required
license	Open License (e.g. Creative Commons), All rights reserved	Controlled List, incl. machine-readable URL of the license	Required
publication date	Publication Date in ISO format	Following ISO standard	Required
place of publication	Place of Publication	Free text	Required
publication format	clear denomination of publication format (PDF, ePub, HTML, etc.)	Controlled Vocabulary, with the option to add free text	Required
publisher / imprint (if applica	Publisher name, URL, ROR (encouraged)	Free text plus ROR PID	Required
DOI	DOI URL	Well-formatted DOI following best practice	Required
landing Page URL	DOI and/or Landing Page URL (where DOI is not used)	URL. Highly relevant in the context of collating usage statistics across multiple OA platforms	Required
full-text URL	URL of the full text document (link to the publication file, e.g. PDF, epub)	URL. Highly relevant in the context of collating usage statistics across multiple OA platforms	Required
page range (for chapters)		free text (to enable Roman numerals and other variations next to Arabic numbers)	Required
language	to indicate language(s) used in the publication	Controlled list following ISO standard	Required
ISBN	Book-level ISBNs (ideally one ISBN per book format)	standardised input, ideally via ISBN check upon entry	Required
ISSN	for serial publications	standardised	Required
subject codes / headings	via controlled vocabularies such as Thema or VIAF, free-text keyword option also enabled	Multiple controlled vocabularies, or free-text keyword as fallback	Required
metadata record license	Explicit mention of the license applied to a given metadata record, to enable downstream re-use	Standardised CC0 or other public domain dedication in both human- and machine-readable form	Required
Desired			
cover image URLs	URL where the cover image can be accessed	URL	Recommended
table of contents	in free-text, Markdown, or JATS XML	Free text, preformatted (see desc.)	Recommended
abstract	in free-text, Markdown, or JATS XML	Free text, with possibility to record in multiple languages	Recommended
references / works cited	on the level of the book and/or individual chapters	CSV (can be a list of referenced DOIs at minimum)	Recommended
Contributor PIDs	ORCID where available; ISNI as alternative	ORCID number or full URL to profile	Recommended
Affiliated institution of Co:	ROR	ROR ID or full URL to profile	Recommended
Funder information	ROR (to supersede Funder Registry)	ROR ID or full URL to profile	Recommended
Location URLs	Content URLs from the various platforms that OA content has been disseminated to	URL	Recommended
	ARK as alternative PID	ARK ID or full URL	Optional
	ISNI as alternative PID	ISNI ID or full URL	Optional
Multilingual versions of metadata	Enabling publishers from different regional contexts to record metadata in other languages than English		Recommended
Peer-review status	Indicate the type of peer review applied to a given title.	Could be using PRISM framework, or other ways to denote peer-review status.	Optional
Crossmark	(for publishers using Crossref)	See Crossref guidance for more details	Optional
Source:	International metadata recommendations, and platform-specific requirements for open access books and chapters (2026)		
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